

ACTION RESEARCH IN ENGLISH TEACHER TRAINING: FLIPPED TEACHING, COOPERATIVE LEARNING, AND PEER ASSESSMENT

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Abstract

The present article shares the experience from applying Flipped Teaching, Cooperative Learning, and Peer Assessment at Kostanay A. Baitursynuly Regional University during 2023-2024 academic year, when all three cycles of Action Research were carried out. Tertiary students who are in their third year of four and are being trained to become English teachers, total number 137 students from 12 groups, were the participants of the research during their English Teaching Methodology Course. The Action Research data was collected through observation, interviews, questionnaires, and testing. As a result, high learning outcomes were achieved that was objectively confirmed in the final assessment through Moodle test.

Keywords: Action Research; English Teacher Training; Flipped Classroom; Cooperative Learning; Peer Assessment

Introduction

The present article describes the authentic educational experience integrated into the professional preparation of prospective English educators at the Foreign Languages Department of the Pedagogical Institute under Umyrzak Sultangazin at Akhmet Baitursynuly Regional University, throughout the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year. The training of teachers stands as a pivotal aspect of educational advancement globally, necessitating ongoing evolution and enhancement, particularly within student-centric environments. Often it requires Cross-Disciplinarity, as in other jobs training since teachers tend to be universally educated people, who do not only learn effectively themselves, but also can facilitate their students; educational efforts in the future. [1-3] Every effort is taken to ensure best practices in teaching are not talked about, but demonstrated in the real-life teaching process and students' internship training that follows the theoretical study. [4-5] Reflective thinking skills [6-7] have recently become a universally recognized crucial part of university teaching, so we chose to employ Action Research to see whether the methods that are chosen for one of the central courses in future teachers' training are effective and productive. The strategies delineated henceforth were deliberately selected and subsequently implemented within one of the primary subjects of the educational program 6B01705 "Foreign Language: Two Foreign Languages," specifically focusing on English Teaching Methodology.

Methods

The Action Research [8,9] was carried out to observe whether application of Flipped Teaching, Cooperative Learning, and Peer Assessment would be beneficial for achieving high levels of students' learning outcomes. *Observation checklists* were used by the

teacher to keep the record of the educational process and a few times visiting colleagues completed their own observation sheets to register students' involvement into the lectures and seminars. Critical thinking lied in the base of the Action Research procedure.[9] Brief *interviews with students* from each of 12 groups were conducted three times: in the first week, in week 8 after the first attestation period, and in week 15 prior to examination. It helped us move on from expectations to generative uncertainties in teaching and learning activities. [10] Students' feedback was taken into account and minor changes were introduced into the training: students preferred to stay in the same micro groups rather than change partners for every seminar, and short video recordings for personal publications in students' social networks were approved. *Questionnaires* were suggested to students twice in Google forms and were not obligatory. However, a lot of students chose to express their opinions concerning microteaching sessions and evaluate their course upon its completion. *Testing* was used in the form of short weekly tests for particular topics covered during each week and the summative assessment: twice in the semester, in weeks 7 and 15 for intermediate attestation and for the final examination. Test questions were teacher created and formed the test bank of 500 questions.

The teaching methods specified complemented each other in the course: lectures built on the *Flipped Classroom* led to interactive discussions; Group work at the seminars increased student talking time manifold as students shared their findings in the course. As XXX rightly points out, "Teaching and learning are best accomplished through the novel and blended approaches in today's smart manufacturing, services, and labor processes." [11] *Cooperative learning* proved both popular with students and engaging, as there were

hot discussions on many teaching issues throughout the course. Working in groups of five, alternating for each class, students discussed seminar questions and did micro-teaching sessions with subsequent peer assessment. The same as Qing Xie (2023) stated, in our setting “the participants considered teamwork and group cooperation to be their most improved skills, along with other soft skills and practice abilities.”[12] Demonstrating rather than explaining methods useful for student-centered learning is what we find working for a tertiary Methodology course. Lectures turned into interactive discussions instead of teacher talking time and group work at the seminars required change in the assessment procedures as well. Naturally we referred to the peer assessment. *Peer assessment* was based on the rubrics with assessment criteria created by the teacher in cooperation with the students and thus ensured thorough preparation, active participation, and discussion at the seminars and lectures.

Discussion

This approach was debated in the Foreign Languages Chair meetings and not universally approved. Such organization involved too much responsibility on students who had to make decisions assessing each other, some of the faculty said. However, since students are trained to be English and German teachers, assessment is likely to be easier in future. As students divided the seminar questions between them, they had to teach each other the content they were responsible for. This also contributed to their teacher training agenda – explaining their peers both theory and demonstrating the methods in 15-minute micro-teaching sessions was highly efficient.

Let's delve into each of these teaching methods and how they proved beneficial for teacher training. *Flipped Teaching* ensured active learning, critical thinking, and personalized learning. Flipped teaching encourages active engagement with course materials outside of class time. The course teacher modeled some effective instructional techniques, such as creating engaging pre-recorded lectures shared through the Moodle page, assigned relevant readings, which aspiring teachers then analyzed and emulated. Critical Thinking was apparent in a variety of educational situations: by shifting traditional lecture content to pre-class activities, flipped teaching freed up valuable class time for deeper discussions, problem-solving activities, and critical thinking exercises. This approach helped aspiring teachers develop their own critical thinking skills, which are essential for effective teaching and lesson planning. Personalized Learning was a natural part of Flipped teaching, as it allowed aspiring teachers to progress through course materials at their own pace and revisit challenging concepts as needed. This personalized approach accommodates diverse learning styles and fosters a sense of autonomy and responsibility in teacher trainees.

Cooperative Learning involved collaboration skills development; it also provided social interaction increase in the otherwise dull learning environment and opened diverse perspectives on the material studied. Collaboration Skills: Cooperative learning promotes collaboration, teamwork, and communication skills among teacher trainees. Through group activities, aspiring teachers learn to work effectively with their peers, share ideas, and resolve conflicts constructively—skills that are essential for fostering positive classroom environments.

Social Interaction: Teacher training involves more than just acquiring knowledge; it also requires developing interpersonal skills. Cooperative learning activities provide opportunities for aspiring teachers to interact socially, build relationships, and empathize with their peers and future students.

Diverse Perspectives: Working in groups exposes teacher trainees to diverse perspectives, teaching styles, and problem-solving approaches. By engaging with peers from different backgrounds, aspiring teachers gain insights into alternative teaching methods and develop a deeper understanding of educational diversity and inclusivity.

Peer Assessment served to develop feedback skills, professional growth and served the basis for community building. Feedback Skills: Peer assessment encourages aspiring teachers to provide constructive feedback to their peers and reflect on their own teaching practices. By evaluating each other's work, teacher trainees develop valuable assessment and feedback skills, which are essential for fostering continuous improvement and self-reflection.

Professional Growth: Receiving feedback from peers can be a powerful catalyst for professional growth. Aspiring teachers can gain valuable insights into their strengths and areas for improvement, identify teaching strategies that resonate with their peers, and refine their instructional techniques accordingly.

Community Building: Peer assessment fosters a sense of community and mutual support among teacher trainees. By actively participating in the assessment process, aspiring teachers demonstrate respect for their peers' expertise and contribute to a collaborative learning environment conducive to growth and development.

Results

Microteaching session evaluation was conducted in the form of Google Form questionnaire and received 27 answers. The question “Assess how hard you worked during the micro-teaching session in groups” most of the students answered either “Hard” or “Very hard”, two people assessed themselves as either “Hardly” or “A little” The diagram below shows the percentage (see diagram 1):

Diagram 1. Students' self-assessment of effort put into group work

Your self-assessment

Assessment of class organization for the micro-teaching session also received mostly positive feedback, see diagram 2:

Diagram 2. Students' assessment of the class organization

Your assessment of the class organization

Students assessed each other's teaching in the micro-teaching sessions against a number of criteria:

- The trainee teacher 1 had a lesson plan
- Vocabulary presentation was clear
- There were at least 4 exercises for consolidation
- Time management was effective
- Vocabulary choice was appropriate

- The trainee teacher 1 gave feedback for every exercise
 - There was a communicative activity at the end
- The results of assessment of another student's teaching can be seen in Diagram 3:
Diagram 3. Students' peer assessment of micro-teaching vocabulary session

Your assessment of the trainee teacher 1

To the question “What was that you liked about the class?” students answered (some of the answers are quoted): “I liked the fact that we all took part in the tasks.”; “I liked that everyone was engaged in teaching activities, exercises and we were helping each other with understanding the material”; “Training itself”; “I really liked the atmosphere in the class, it was friendly, everyone supported each other. trainee teachers who performed, very well and responsibly prepared. and did a great job”; “It included some new words for me and may be even it was a new (unusual) type of presentation of some material that I will be able to practice later”; “The opportunity to give a lesson to my group mates”.

To the question “What you would change to make it more productive?” there were some constructive criticism responses, like “To do more exercises; trying to be more clear in speaking and communication with students”; “Add more speaking and it would be better if

we had more time”; “I would give more time to students so that everyone could reveal their abilities”; “Conduct games on the relevant topic of the lesson”; “I would like microteaching to last more than 15 minutes.”; “show instruction for the first lesson plan so that it will be clearer for students how to do it”; “We need online ZOOM meeting lessons”; “We should strictly follow the time frames for each student, so that everyone had the possibility to train how to teach”; “show instruction for the first lesson plan so that it will be clearer for students how to do it”. The other responses noted that students were satisfied with the micro-teaching session organization.

The answers to the question “Would you like to have more lessons like this?” encouraged the teacher to continue with this lesson mode (see Diagram 4):

Diagram 4. Students’ overall assessment of the micro-teaching organization

Would you like to have more classes like this?

27 ответов

The other questionnaire was suggested to students on their completion of the course and received 52 answers. The first question “Level of effort” asked for students’ self-evaluation of how much effort they had put into studying the course, the results are presented in Diagram 5 below:

Diagram 5. Students’ self-evaluation of the effort they had put into the course.

Level of effort

The second question “Contribution to learning” asked how much the course had contributed to their learning. Results are presented in Diagram 6 below:

Diagram 6. Students’ assessment of the course’s contribution to their learning.

Contribution to learning

52 ответа

The question “Skill and responsiveness of the instructor” was aimed at receiving students’ feedback to the effectiveness of teaching and results are shown in Diagram 7 below:

Diagram 7. Skill and responsiveness of the instructor.

Skill and responsiveness of the instructor

The next question was to have students assess the Course content; the results are presented below in Diagram 8. Students assessment of the course content.

Course content

The question “What aspects of this course were most useful or valuable?” received 45 answers, sample answers are presented here: “For me, it was to write a lesson plan and conduct a lesson for group-mates. Thanks to this, I have gained experience and can figure out how to teach a lesson in practice and at school.” “Applying teaching in practice, improving presentation skills, having an opportunity for creativity”; “I liked our seminars where my classmates and I shared our knowledge. it was an interesting approach to learning, more interesting and useful in my opinion than traditional seminars”; “Practical part when we write lesson plans”; “the opportunity to repeat everything in the middle, tests, a combination of practical classes and online platforms”; “How to learn and teach in different ways, how to be a good teacher”; “Teaching Methods, Tips about particular situations in the class room”; “teaching methods, knowledge about the types of students (kinesthetics, visuals, etc.) Your lessons and lectures were really interesting to attend, thank you!”; “it was useful that we exchanged views, the presentations of group mates were very interesting”.

The question seeking criticism was formulated “How would you improve this course?” received 39 answers some of them are quoted here: “I’ve worked on my pronunciation.” “To Use more forms of working in classroom, to vary tasks”; “I think, we can make a list of best students every month (maybe, it will increase students’ motivation) like a competition.” “Add more explanation according to the references (how to organize them in the course paper)” “I think we need more control over the quality of students’ completing assignments”; “I would add some more creative tasks. such as association, poster protection, etc.” “Maybe group projects”.

Moodle test was conducted as the final assessment procedure. Students were tested in the university test room and were supervised by the surveillance video cameras and human observers, as it is the general requirement. The test consisted of 40 questions, randomly chosen by the testing system from the bank of 500 questions. The maximum test score was 100, the time assigned for testing was an hour. Quality of the

result constituted 85.4%: out of 137 students in the course, 117 got marks in the range of 70-100, 14 got satisfactory (50-69) and 6 students failed. We believe these results prove efficiency of the methods applied to the course.

Conclusion

Action research is a powerful methodology employed by educators to enhance teaching practices and improve student learning outcomes. We believe, it contributes to the improvement of teaching in a number of ways, ensures reflective practice, allows targeted problem solving, leads the teacher to evidence-based decision making, guarantees continuous improvement, professional growth and establishes collaborative learning communities. Action research encouraged us to reflect on the teaching methods we were using, on classroom dynamics, and student engagement. By systematically examining their own practices, teachers gain insights into what works well and what needs improvement. It allows teachers to identify specific challenges or areas of improvement within their teaching practice. Whether it's addressing student motivation, refining instructional strategies, or adapting to diverse learning needs, action research helps teachers pinpoint where interventions are needed. Through action research, we were able to collect and analyze data related to teaching and learning. This data serves as evidence to inform decision-making processes. By basing decisions on empirical evidence rather than intuition alone, teachers can make more informed choices about instructional approaches. Action research is iterative in nature, involving cycles of planning, acting, observing, and reflecting. This continuous improvement cycle allows teachers to gradually refine their teaching practices over time. By making small, incremental changes and assessing their impact, educators can steadily enhance the effectiveness of their teaching. Engaging in action research fosters professional growth and development among educators. By actively investigating and addressing challenges within their practice, teachers expand their knowledge, skills, and expertise. This ongoing process of inquiry promotes a culture of lifelong learning within the teaching profession. Collaborative

Learning Community was strengthened through this action research, as it involved collaboration among teachers within our department. By working together on common goals and sharing findings, teachers can leverage collective expertise and support one another in improving teaching practices. This collaborative approach fosters a sense of community and shared responsibility for student success. Overall, action research empowers educators to take ownership of their professional development and drive meaningful improvements in teaching and learning. By adopting a systematic and reflective approach to inquiry, teachers can enhance their effectiveness in the classroom and ultimately contribute to positive educational outcomes for students.

In summary, flipped teaching, cooperative learning, and peer assessment offered unique benefits for teacher training, including promoting active learning, critical thinking, collaboration, communication, feedback skills, and professional growth. By integrating these methods into teacher training programs, educators can better prepare aspiring teachers for the challenges and opportunities they will encounter in the classroom.

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